

Perceptual Coding of High-Resolution Fingertip Tactile Feedback

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Abstract—This paper presents a perceptual tactile codec designed for high-resolution tactile feedback at the fingertip. Unlike previous methods that primarily target single-point vibrotactile compression, our approach addresses the efficient transmission of high-resolution, multi-point tactile signals. We first preprocess the tactile signal to extract force field information, including normal and two orthogonal shear forces. By mapping the three channels of force data to a YUV format video stream, the data becomes compatible with standard video processing pipelines. To improve perceptual realism, we introduce a ROI-aware adaptive quantization method that considers the varying sensitivity across different regions of the fingertip. More bits are allocated to areas that are perceptually more important. We evaluate the performance of our method using ROI-PSNR and perceptual quality metrics, including weighted ROI-PSNR and HPW-PSNR. The results demonstrate that our approach outperforms the baseline HEVC coding scheme across all evaluation criteria.

Index Terms—tactile codec, perceptual coding, tactile internet.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Tactile Internet facilitates real-time physical interaction with remote environments and enables the transmission of human skills [1]. To provide realistic haptic experiences, especially in precision tasks such as remote surgery and teleoperation, it is necessary to transmit tactile signals with high spatial resolution. High contact point density has been shown to improve shape recognition performance by providing richer haptic cues [2]. However, the real-time transmission of rich tactile data presents significant challenges in terms of rate requirements and latency constraints.

Recent advances in high-resolution tactile sensing (e.g., DIGIT [3], GelSight [4] and TacLINK [5]) and haptic rendering devices (e.g., HaptX [6], a finger-mounted high-density pin-array [7]) have enhanced our ability to capture and convey fine-grained tactile information. Consider a representative teleoperation scenario as shown in Fig. 1. An operator remotely

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controls a robotic hand to grasp and manipulate objects. During interaction, robotic fingertip sensors capture vision-based tactile signals, which are encoded and transmitted to the operator. On the operator side, these signals are processed and rendered by a haptic device to provide tactile feedback. These sensors produce large-scale, continuous data streams. For example, ten DIGIT sensors operating at 30 Hz with 240×320 RGB resolution can generate more than 550 Mbps of raw vision-based tactile data. Therefore, an efficient tactile compression algorithm is essential.

Conventional video codecs such as H.264/AVC and H.265/HEVC can be used to compress vision-based tactile signals, but they are designed for visual perception and may not preserve perceptually important tactile information. Moreover, raw tactile frames often contain irrelevant colorful backgrounds, leading to inefficient compression and unnecessary computation. Overcoming these challenges calls for a perception-aware tactile codec.

In this paper, we propose a perceptual codec for vision-based high-resolution tactile signals. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first vision-based tactile codec guided by human tactile perception. First, we preprocess the vision-based tactile signal to extract and transmit force field data, specifically, normal and shear forces, removing redundant sensor background in raw images. This allows us to directly map the force field data to the haptic device. Second, we define the regions of interest (ROIs) based on contact regions. To preserve perceptual fidelity, quantization parameters are adaptively assigned for each coding unit (CU), with higher precision applied to sensitive regions. Finally, we use ROI-PSNR and perceptual metrics to demonstrate that our method achieves superior performance compared to straightforward HEVC encoding of the vision-based tactile signals.

In summary, the contributions of this paper are:

- We propose a perceptual codec for vision-based tactile data.
- We develop an ROI-aware adaptive quantization strategy based on tactile sensitivity.
- Experiments show that our proposed method outperforms HEVC in both objective and perceptual metrics.

Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed perceptual codec pipeline. The pipeline involves four main stages: (a) Data Acquisition: Vision-based tactile sensors capture raw data. (b) Preprocessing: Normal and shear force fields are extracted from the raw data. (c) Perceptual Coding and Transmission: The force fields are perceptually encoded, compressed, and sent over the communication network. (d) Haptic Rendering: The received data is decoded and rendered on a high-resolution haptic display to recreate the tactile sensation. The tactile sensor and display images are adapted from [3] and [7] respectively.

II. RELATED WORK

Driven by the increasing importance of haptic communication, several standardization efforts have been initiated, notably IEEE 1918.1.1 [8] and MPEG-I Haptics Coding [9]. At the same time, academic research has driven the development of a range of novel tactile codec designs. Most existing tactile codecs focus on vibrotactile signals, including transform-based approaches such as PVC-SLP [10] and VC-PWQ [11], as well as an autoencoder-based method [12] and its rate-scalable variant [13]. In addition, deep learning architectures such as GRU [14], CNN [15], and N-BEATS [16] have also been investigated for vibrotactile signal compression. However, these methods are limited to handling vibrotactile signals from a single contact point. To overcome these limitations, recent research has focused on multi-point [17] and multi-modal [18] tactile compression. The multi-channel vibrotactile codec MVibCode leverages inter-channel redundancies using channel clustering and differential coding [17]. Ogura et al. [19] proposed a joint source-channel coding scheme for multichannel vibrotactile signals.

Another effort in multi-point tactile compression was made by Li et al. [20]. They established the Multi-Point Tactile Dataset for Dexterous Hand Grasping (Dex-MPTD) and investigated the performance of existing image compression techniques on this dataset by converting tactile data into image formats. However, their method converts tactile data to images only after a complete manipulation process, making real-time encoding impossible.

Although some recent efforts have explored multi-point tactile compression, research on vision-based tactile signal compression remains limited. Chen et al. [21] incorporated visual assistance to detect blank frames and enhance compression through specialized intra/inter-frame encoding. However, current research on codecs for high-density vision-based tactile

signals has yet to systematically consider human tactile perception, which is essential for maintaining perceptual fidelity under compression.

Studies on human tactile perception are beneficial for designing effective tactile codecs. Jaroka et al. established that first-order tactile neurons can resolve spatial details on the scale of a single fingerprint ridge (around 0.4 mm) [22]. Furthermore, research has shown that tactile sensitivity is non-uniform across the fingertip pad [23]. He and Liu [24] designed experiments to establish a predictive model for the perceptual importance of various tactile channels on the hand. These understandings of spatial tactile perception are especially important for optimizing multiple touch points.

III. METHOD

A. Preprocessing

We use a dedicated preprocessing method and propose a perceptual codec for vision-based tactile sequences, as illustrated in Fig. 1. To begin with, we use the pre-trained Sparsh model [25] to process the raw vision-based tactile input data captured by the DIGIT sensor. This model extracts a dense force field that captures both normal and shear force components on the contact surface, illustrated in Fig. 2. These extracted force fields serve as a compact and physically meaningful representation of tactile interaction. This preprocessing step offloads most of the computational burden to the data acquisition stage, enabling lightweight decoding and rendering on the client side. The resulting force field can be directly mapped to actuator arrays on haptic devices, facilitating real-time tactile playback without the need for heavy post-processing. Furthermore, preprocessing enables effective foreground-background separation, isolating contact regions and discarding irrelevant background color information.

The extracted normal and shear forces are then mapped to an 8-bit YUV 4:4:4 video stream, with the spatial resolution pre-

Fig. 2: Visualization of the force field extraction from a raw vision-based sensor frame. Left: the raw tactile image captured by the DIGIT sensor. Middle: normal force represented as a heatmap where brighter areas indicate higher pressure. Right: shear force, visualized as a vector field.

served at 240×320 pixels. This format allows us to use mature video compression and processing techniques in the following step. The following sections describe how the H.265/HEVC codec is optimized for the perceptual characteristics of tactile data to ensure high-quality and efficient transmission.

B. Spatial Sensitivity on Fingertip

Tactile sensitivity varies significantly across different regions of the body, as illustrated by the well-known cortical homunculus [26]. This spatial distribution indicates that certain areas of the body contribute more prominently to tactile perception. Leveraging this knowledge can enable more efficient compression of tactile signals, particularly in scenarios involving large-area or multi-point contact, by allocating resources according to perceptual relevance. Since vision-based tactile sensors are typically used as fingertip sensors on robotic hands, we focus on perception in the human fingertip region. On the finger scale, Abad et al. [23] examined the differences in sensitivity within the fingertip by dividing it into seven distinct areas. Their results, averaged over five fingertips, show that the finger pulp (area G) is among the most sensitive regions, while the front of the finger (area C) presents relatively low sensitivity, as presented in Fig. 3a. Although sensitivity differs across fingertip regions, it may remain consistent across different fingers. Based on these findings, we adopted the same regional division for our sensor layout, shown in Fig. 3b, and computed the sensitivity and weight for each area.

TABLE I: Sensitivity and corresponding weight across different areas of the distal phalanx

Area	Force (mN)	Sensitivity	Weight
A	0.686	1.457	0.903
B	0.392	2.549	1.205
C	1.569	0.637	0.676
D	0.686	1.457	0.903
E	0.686	1.457	0.903
F	0.392	2.549	1.205
G	0.392	2.549	1.205

Sensitivity S_i is defined as the inverse of the minimal force F_i required for a participant to detect a stimulus:

$$S_i = \frac{1}{F_i} \quad (1)$$

(a) Sensitivity across fingers and areas. Areas with lighter colors represent lower absolute perception thresholds, meaning they are more sensitive. Reproduced from [23] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

(b) Segmenting the sensor area.

Fig. 3: Distal phalanx sensitivity.

Areas that are more sensitive require less force to detect a stimulus and thus have higher S_i values. We normalize each sensitivity across all n areas to obtain a dimensionless weight r_i , which represents the relative sensitivity of area i compared to the average sensitivity:

$$r_i = \frac{S_i}{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n S_j} \quad (2)$$

To prevent excessively large or small weights while preserving relative differences, we apply a linear deviation-scaling step centered at 1 to calculate weights. Without this step, bit allocation may become uneven, leading to an imbalanced focus where some regions are over-emphasized while others are neglected. Furthermore, this imbalance may introduce noticeable discontinuities at the boundaries between regions with different weights.

$$W_i = 1 + c(r_i - 1), \quad 0 < c \leq 1, \quad (3)$$

where W_i is the weight of region i and c is a user-specified shrinking factor. In this study, we choose $c = 0.5$, which compresses the original range of $r_i \in [0.353, 1.410]$ to $W_i \in [0.676, 1.205]$. The minimal forces F_i , computed sensitivities S_i , and weights W_i are summarized in Table I.

The region-specific weighting helps preserve the quality of perceptually important areas in the method presented below.

C. Perception-Guided ROI-based Tactile Signal Compression

We propose a novel perception-aware quality adaptation strategy for tactile signal compression, which includes 3 steps: 1) tactile ROI extraction, 2) perceptually weighted mapping, and 3) CU-adaptive quantization. This technique preserves high-resolution details in perceptually critical fingertip regions while reducing the resolution of other areas. Our method explicitly models the spatial non-uniformity of tactile perception to optimize subjective quality within bandwidth constraints.

We first extract tactile-based regions of interest (ROIs) corresponding to foreground areas in the force field. Pixels without contact force are classified as background and excluded from subsequent analysis. To identify the foreground, we generate a binary mask by thresholding each force-field frame pixel against a minimum value:

$$mask_F(i, j) = \begin{cases} 1, & F(i, j) > F_{\text{thresh}} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Here, F_{thresh} is set to 5% of the maximum value in the current frame. This effectively filters out background regions with negligible force magnitudes, ensuring all downstream processing focuses exclusively on active contact zones.

(a) Raw tactile video frame. (b) Corresponding CU partitioning and perception-driven QP.

Fig. 4: Perception-aware Quantization Parameter (QP) distribution.

Next, we construct a pixel-level perceptual significance map by multiplying the binary mask with the perceptual weight $W(i, j)$:

$$M(i, j) = mask_F(i, j) \times W(i, j) \quad (5)$$

where $W(i, j)$ encodes the location-dependent tactile sensitivity computed in the last subsection. Within the HEVC framework, each frame is partitioned into Coding Units (CUs). For each CU, we calculate an average perceptual score:

$$score_{CU} = \frac{1}{|CU|} \sum_{(i, j) \in CU} M(i, j) \quad (6)$$

where $|CU|$ is the number of pixels in the CU. This scalar score quantifies the perceptual importance of each CU for tactile reconstruction fidelity, with higher values indicating

greater perceptual importance. Finally, we perform CU-level quantization parameter (QP) adaptation based on perceptual significance scores:

$$QP_{CU} = \begin{cases} QP - 1 & score_{CU} > T_1 \\ QP & T_2 < score_{CU} \leq T_1 \\ QP + 3 & 0 < score_{CU} \leq T_2 \\ QP + 5 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where T_1 and T_2 are thresholds used to determine the perceptually adaptive QP. The limited ΔQP range per CU is a deliberate design choice, aiming to balance the flexibility of the encoding with the coherence of the tactile quality. This strategy preserves higher encoding quality in perceptually important regions, improving the tactile feedback experience.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Dataset

We collected a custom tactile dataset using a DIGIT sensor by sliding it across the surfaces of 10 everyday objects with diverse geometries and textures. The selected objects—bottle cap, box, coin, key, mouse, mug, pen, scissors, screwdriver, and tape—were chosen to represent a wide range of contact conditions and material properties. Data were captured in the sensor default settings, 30 Hz sampling rate and 240×320 resolution. For each object, we recorded approximately 1,000 frames. To ensure comprehensive coverage and robustly capture diverse contact dynamics, data collection involved varied sliding orientations and contact pressures, covering different surface types such as tips, edges, and flat areas.

B. Experiment Configuration

For baseline comparison, we adopted the HM 18.0 reference software as the HEVC implementation. To meet the real-time transmission requirements, we configured the encoder in Low Delay (LD) mode. The Group of Pictures (GOP) size was set to 8. The input format was set to 8-bit YUV 4:4:4, matching the preprocessed tactile video. We tested several quantization parameters ($QP = 22, 27, 32, 37, 42$) to evaluate rate-distortion performance. For a fair comparison, our proposed codec follows the same low-latency configurations, using identical frame resolution and bit depth. The thresholds T_1 and T_2 in (7) were set to 1.0 and 0.8, respectively.

C. Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate reconstruction quality, we used ROI-PSNR, weighted ROI-PSNR and Haptic Perceptually Weighted Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (HPW-PSNR) as metrics. The last two metrics are related to perception. These metrics focus on the sensor contact region, which is the area that transmits meaningful haptic information. Regions outside the contact area contain no tactile signal (zero force) and can be easily reconstructed by codecs due to their uniform values. Frames without any contact region are excluded from PSNR computation. The region of interest (ROI) for each frame is dynamically extracted based on the contact mask derived from (4).

Weighted ROI-PSNR further incorporates fingertip sensitivity, assigning higher weights to central or more sensitive areas within the contact patch, based on a predefined tactile sensitivity map. This better reflects perceptual importance and aligns with our codec’s design goals.

HPW-PSNR [27] was designed to better reflect human perception in evaluating haptic signal quality by incorporating the concept of just noticeable difference (JND). It measures signal distortion in a way that aligns with what users perceive, offering a more perceptually meaningful evaluation. The mathematical definition of HPW-PSNR is given by:

$$\text{HPW-PSNR} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{\|v_{\max} - v_{\min}\|^2}{\text{MSE} \cdot \text{HPW}} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{HPW} = \begin{cases} C & \text{if } |v - \hat{v}| \leq \text{JND}(v) \\ k \cdot (|v - \hat{v}| - \text{JND}(v)) + C & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where v_{\max} and v_{\min} are the maximum and minimum values of the original signal v . C is a constant that represents the perceptual cost within the JND threshold. k is a penalty factor that scales the error exceeding the JND. $\text{JND}(v) = a_v \cdot |v|$, where a_v is the percentage of tolerable degradation of signal values. We compute the HPW-PSNR for the ROI in each frame and average them. The parameters for HPW-PSNR calculation were set as follows: C was set to 1, the JND scaling factor a_v was set to 0.1, and the penalty weight k was set to 10.

D. Results

Fig. 5 compares our method and standard HEVC on the preprocessed force field video against a baseline of HEVC compressing the original video captured by the DIGIT sensor. The flat curve of the baseline indicates that bitrate is inefficiently spent on irrelevant background details. In contrast, the steep curves of the preprocessed methods demonstrate the efficiency of focusing all coding resources on the essential data. Although the original video maintains a high PSNR at low bitrates, compression artifacts obscure the contact area, potentially degrading the operator’s haptic feedback and task performance. Furthermore, our method (Ours) builds on the advantage of preprocessing, achieving an additional 0.35 dB BD-PSNR improvement over standard HEVC.

Fig. 5: ROI-PSNR.

Fig. 6: Perceptual weighted ROI-PSNR.

Fig. 7: HPW-PSNR.

As depicted in Fig. 6, the weighted ROI PSNR results are consistent with those of the ROI-PSNR. The proposed method improves the average PSNR by 0.59 dB at the same bitrate, according to the BD-PSNR metric. The weighted ROI PSNR metric is more representative of perceptual quality, and the performance gain of our method is more pronounced when evaluated with this metric than with the standard PSNR metric. Despite Region C having the lowest sensitivity and very low weight among all defined areas, its position on the uppermost part of the sensor means that it doesn’t have frequent contact with the object surface. So, it has a limited effect on the computed weighted PSNR.

The HPW-PSNR results are presented in Fig. 7. Compared

Fig. 8: Perceptual weighted ROI-PSNR for each object.

to HEVC, our method demonstrates improved performance in perceptual quality metrics. The HPW-PSNR values are generally lower than PSNR due to the penalty applied to reconstruction errors that exceed the JND threshold.

To address the performance variation across different objects, Fig. 8 presents the individual perceptual weighted ROI-PSNR curves for each of the ten objects. The results demonstrate a robust performance trend across different items.

E. Discussion

The experimental results show that our method outperforms HEVC in both signal-level and perceptual metrics and validate the effectiveness of our perceptual compression strategy. The next step is to conduct comprehensive user studies to better understand the perceptual impact of our approach in real-world scenarios. Promising future directions include the optimization of parameters and preprocessing techniques, as well as an exploration of spatial resolution to provide a theoretical foundation for perceptual quality.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented a novel compression approach for high-resolution multi-point tactile feedback. By extracting both normal and shear force components and incorporating fingertip sensitivity into a ROI-aware quantization framework, our method achieves perceptually meaningful compression. Unlike single-point vibrotactile compression, our codec supports richer and spatially accurate tactile experiences, especially in scenarios that require the perception of shapes and edges. Quantitative evaluations confirm that our method outperforms the HEVC benchmark in both ROI-PSNR and perceptual metrics. In future work, we plan to conduct user studies to assess perceptual quality and integrate our codec into teleoperation systems for remote manipulation tasks.

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